

**Learning to interpret and mediate in the
1·1·2 emergency phone line through roleplay**

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Abstract

Current times compel teachers to constantly improve and renew their teaching practice in the search of active methodologies that meet the high training needs of their students. This paper aims to provide a pragmatic example of how language courses in the Bachelor's Degree in Translation and Interpreting are put at the service of the interpreting activity from an experimental standpoint so that future Translators and Interpreters are able to use tools that guarantee citizens' access to information, to Public Services and, therefore, to the protection of their fundamental rights and freedoms in an equitable manner.

In this study, which takes place at the International University of Valencia (VIU), we bring to the *Language B English* course a didactic proposal based on a simulation game as a method of collaborative and transformative learning. The trainees, following the Emergency Response Protocols and the techniques of Telephonic Dialogue Interpreting and Mediation, will have to solve and recreate a call addressed to the European public emergency telephone "1·1·2". As professional Interpreters and Mediators, they will be the link between the citizen and the Emergency Services of the Public Administration saving, with the power of the word, life itself.

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1. Introduction

The UN Agenda 2030 for Sustainable Development is an action programme for people, the planet and prosperity. Among its main goals and targets, it calls for sustainable, inclusive and egalitarian development. In order to achieve this, alliances between nations are required to promote a spirit of solidarity and inclusion, where the accessibility of citizens to information and all essential services is guaranteed on an equal basis. In this regard, Goal 16 is fundamental since it promotes "peaceful and inclusive societies, providing access to justice for all and building effective, accountable and inclusive institutions at all levels". To this end, among other purposes, it seeks to "ensure public access to information and protect fundamental freedoms, in accordance with national legislation and international agreements" (Target 16.10, UN 2015, 26).

In the broad social and migratory context of our times, it is especially in the area of services necessary for the maintenance of basic social functions, health, security and the social welfare of citizens that more institutional efforts must be made to move towards the achievement of goal 16.10 of the globalist agenda, since equal and universal access to information and communication of all individuals with the Public Administration cannot be understood without quality public language services.

In this regard, Public Service Interpreting (PSI) arose from the need to find solutions to communication problems between public institutions and individuals who do not speak the official languages of the host country (Abril 2006). To date, many research studies have been published (Gentile et al. 1996; Pöschhacker 1999; Corsellis 2008; Valero 2008), which lay the foundations of this translation modality where professionals of translation, interpreting and mediation in public services are positioned as key players to unblock linguistic problems that may hinder access to information and the protection of people's rights.

One of the essential public services that, since its conception in Europe in 1972, has ensured the protection of fundamental freedoms such as the right to life, physical and moral integrity and security of all citizens, is the single emergency telephone number 1·1·2. The EENA (European Emergency Number Association) defines 1·1·2 as "the emergency number in all 27 EU member states, as well as other European countries and elsewhere. People in danger can call 112 24/7 to reach the fire brigade, medical assistance and the police" (EENA 2022).

In Spain, this number plays a vital role in providing a rapid response in emergency situations both in the official and co-official languages and in the main EU languages (French, English and German) in accordance with the provisions of Council Decision 91/396/EEC of 29 July 1991.

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This is possible by virtue of telephone interpreting (TI), “a real-time language service that enables speakers of different languages to communicate by telephone with the assistance of an interpreter via a three-way conference call” (Heh and Quian 1997, 51) and dialogue interpreting (DI), which “serves the minority language users to ensure their access to public services, such as education, healthcare and justice” (Angelelli 2017).

To that effect, even though the role of Mediators and Interpreters in this Public Emergency Service 1·1·2 (henceforth, MIPESs), is yet to be publicly recognised, every citizen located in the Spanish territory, is guaranteed attention in, at least, five possible languages, when their life is at risk.

In order to continue nurturing this complex mechanism of universal attention and protection of citizens in which translators and interpreters manage and convey the flow of information, the university must position itself as an essential social agent, generating and transferring knowledge to create professionals in a comprehensive and adequate manner to the real needs of society. “These social and economic dimensions become central when universities engage in curriculum development that is socially relevant and economically viable” (Angelelli 2017).

Taking into account that the ultimate goal of this official academic programme is to develop Competence of Translation and Interpreting in a cross-disciplinary way, it would seem appropriate to direct our efforts to promote a meaningful and reflective learning experience in all subjects, understood as a whole and not as independent areas. Following this scheme, this graphic shows the foundation upon which all subjects (especially those at the core of this study) should be conceived.

Figure 1. Principles of Linguistic Subjects in the Degree in Translation and Interpreting

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With the concept of *social harmony* in mind (UNESCO 2013), translation and interpreting professionals must be able to strategically use all the tools they have at their disposal to activate the professional abilities that guarantee that all citizens can access information, public services and, therefore, the protection of their fundamental rights and freedoms in an egalitarian manner. Our mission, as professors in the Degree in Translation and Interpreting, is to guarantee the preparation of these scholars using active methodologies that encourage reflection and the transference of skills from one area to another.

Following the outline in figure 1, a booklet was designed (see Appendix 1 with the link in the footnote¹) for the *Language B English* class with activities which would build on each other increasing the level of difficulty so that learners would be able to simulate emergency call addressed to the life-saving 1·1·2 line at the end of the learning episode.

While performing the tasks, the future MIPESs will have to deal with this request following the protocols stipulated for both Emergency Response and Telephonic Dialogue Interpreting and Mediation, in an efficient manner in English (Language B) and Spanish (Language A) as it would be managed in the Call Answering Room of a Spanish Emergency Coordination Centre.

Ultimately, with this roleplay as a methodological approach, the value of these professionals in building an accessible and sustainable world will also be placed.

2. Objectives

With this teaching philosophy ahead, this paper aims to implement a didactic proposal that could exemplify how language subjects in the Degree in Translation and Interpreting can develop Competence of Translation and Interpreting from a practical, real and adequate perspective.

On the one hand, it seems indispensable to adapt the materials and resources to the specific training needs of the pupils of this programme and, on the other hand, to focus on the skills required to improving mediation and dialogue interpreting in public services while meeting the high social expectations established by the UN within the framework of the Sustainable Development Goals and Democratic Competences (Council of Europe 2016).

Li (2001, 343), like many other authors, expresses his concern about the approach to these subjects in these official studies, interpreting

¹ https://gplaneta-my.sharepoint.com/:b:/g/personal/uvag2a_psoplaneta_com/EXgYHRi5Vq1Er3fqMEHQFIAB8hXVtI_qdwGaZWOPyb43UQ?e=IkIPTI

and “translation programmes should provide effective, tailor-made language courses for translation students”.

As teachers, we know that these courses are the perfect environment to work not only on bilingual and communicative competence but also on other subcompetences such as extralinguistic, instrumental and strategic competence (Clouet 2010). Therefore, it is fundamental to shift the focus to a competence-based approach zooming in on issues related to translation (and we add, interpreting) in real contexts and to propose a model that counteracts the neglect that these subjects have experienced (Carrasco Flores 2019).

Thus, having established the foundations of these subjects within the SDG framework (figure 1), we aim to develop a pedagogical design that follows the current trend in the field of translation and interpreting studies in terms of the way foreign language teaching is conceived, including objectives that contribute to a specific language teaching in the training of translators and interpreters (Berenguer Estellés 1999; Mackenzie 1998; Argüeso 1998; Brehm & Hurtado 1999; Pérez González 1999; Möller 2001; Andreu & Orero 2001; Beeby 2004; Mulligan 2006; Soriano 2004; Clouet & Wood 2008; Cruz García and Adams 2008; Hernández Guerra and Cruz García 2009; Clouet 2010, among others).

3. Sample and participants

The learners who took part in this study belong to the official Degree in Translation and Interpreting at VIU, during the academic year 2022-2023 and performed the roleplay simulation as part of the *Language B English 2 and 4* courses, equivalent to a level B2 and C1 of the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFR), respectively. Both have a course load of 6 ECTS.

The learning sequence was developed during two sessions of two hours each, was taught by the author of this article and took place in a virtual, online and synchronous environment. A multicultural group of 16 scholars were actively involved in the sessions, with age ranging from 25 to 50 years old.

The participants had different language backgrounds, including bilingual or native speakers of English (5), Spanish (9), Russian (1) and Romanian (1). In turn, all of them spoke second and third languages: Spanish (5), English (11), French (14), Italian (2) and German (5). The places of residence were varied, 3 lived in Spain and 13 in other countries such as Mexico (2), Ecuador (1), Peru (1), Argentina (2), France (2), Italy (1), United Kingdom (2) and USA (2). Ten of them had previous experience in the field of translation, while 6 had never worked in this domain.

4. Research methodology

The research methodology followed during this study is mainly qualitative, reviewing the existing literature and trying to test the objectives by developing an action plan in the classroom in order to analyse the impact of our goals and reach valid conclusions (Hernández-Sampieri et al. 2008). The method used aims to test the arguments from an empirical point of view, using collaborative teaching practices in the key ODS with university students.

Thus, we implemented roleplay as a didactic proposal to train interpreters (Tebble 2009), and following Morales-Vallejo's (2012) indications about sample size, with this analysis we seek to continue with the challenge of methodological innovation and obtain indicative data about the effectiveness and weaknesses of the proposal.

A space for the quantitative aspect of the research entails analysing data collected through a questionnaire administered to the participants at the end of the learning episode by way of self-assessment.

5. Didactic approach

The methodological premises used to carry out the tasks, were framed within the Valencian International University (VIU) model, which has an e-learning character, where live sessions are combined with autonomous work. During the synchronous conferences, the course contents are presented; the fundamental concepts, discussed, and case analysis, conducted.

This synchronous work in the language courses is based on self-study using digital coursebooks (with self-correcting tasks) through which learners self-pace their own progress while acquiring linguistic knowledge (grammar and vocabulary) and practise receptive skills such as oral and written comprehension. This online teaching modality is conducted through the platform *Blackboard Collaborate Ultra* and allows the use of the flipped classroom technique, where students work on the contents previously in order to optimise the actual time in the classroom in pursuit of a meaningful learning experience (Berrett 2012; Talbert and Bergmann 2017).

Alongside the linguistic aspects, some concepts will be of particular importance in this simulation game. That is, introducing the learners into the interpreting mode in the emergency phone line, which involves various disciplines: TI, DI and mediation. The following figure shows an overall view of the steps to managing an emergency call. Not only will these different phases determine the contents, but also the stages of the simulation experience.

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Figure 2. Steps to managing a 1·1·2 Emergency call in foreign languages

In order to integrate general and subject-specific competences, promote the connection among each area and prepare trainees for sustainable mediation and interpreting work, we followed the pedagogical recommendations of previous research. Thus, a guided activity based on a simulation exercise was proposed as an effective method of Problem Based Learning (PBL) for the acquisition of Dialogue Interpreting (DI) techniques:

In the field of interpreting, many times the discussions on pedagogy characterize some of the skills and strategies that students need to acquire as those related to problem solving. Teachers of DI would find that PBL can prove to be a useful tool when conceptualizing curricula and designing teaching materials for the specific purpose of teaching DI (Angelelli 2017, 38).

These kind of simulation exercises are based on the representation of a model that mimics a real-world process. To make it possible, key information must be provided to enable participants to perform tasks, discuss, negotiate from different points of view and solve a specific problem (Klabbers 2009).

In light of the above, during the simulation we recreated a complex, structured and localised real-life scenario in which communication between citizens and public services had to be mediated by an interpreter. Participants were assigned different roles (witnesses/callers and MIPESs) and were provided with the intratextual and extratextual elements (Nord 1991) needed to solve the citizens' request for help.

At the same time, the e-learning nature of this online university, conditioned the type of roleplay, which was carried out "blending synchronous and asynchronous media including recordings of the

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sessions, and role play within distance learning contexts” (Wills et. al. 2010, 1). Thus, in addition to the live interactions through the online platform, the learners were provided with guided audio-visual material so that they could repeat or perform the remote interpreting practice in a more autonomous way.

In order to foster such students’ autonomy, the learning goals (figures 3 and 4) were also made explicit at the beginning of the session as a strategy for formative and summative assessment.

Figure 3. Task General Objectives

Figure 4. Task Specific Objectives

This didactic approach is also based on the concept of “social sustainability”, which “includes the role of individuals, relationships

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among social groups, the family, collective behaviour, social class, race and ethnicity, health, education, and the role of institutions in society” (Pappas et al. 2012, 54). Hence, according to these authors, it seemed appropriate to use methodologies that “employ a developmental approach using Bloom’s *Taxonomy of Educational Objectives*, which is a way to classify instructional activities or questions as they progress in cognitive difficulty” (Pappas et al. 2012, 55). Therefore, in the design of these objectives, verbs focused on applicability and synthesis (such as *apply* and *create* respectively) were used giving way to active and meaningful learning.

Following this logic, the foundations were laid to develop a Deeper Learning Episode (DLE), in which pupils had the opportunity to connect, understand and internalise concepts as well as consolidate newly acquired knowledge through relevant practical activities to favour the transfer of skills to other situations (Coyle and Meyer 2021).

Finally, this DLE was carefully planned following the principles of scaffolding theory in which, for the sake of progressive learning, prior knowledge was activated, information was provided in a stepwise manner, and examples were provided to students so that they could achieve cognitive growth (Wood 1996).

Figure 5. Summary diagram of the didactic approach

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The final product outcome consisted in the simulation of a call made to the European public emergency telephone number 1·1·2 in which a witness alerts of a traffic accident in a place in a Spanish city. In this case, the request is received by a MIPESs who has to act as a liaison between the citizen and the Public Emergency Services by completing a report in Spanish for the latter, while maintaining the telephone conversation in English with the citizen. The activity took place in four stages: introduction and information (session 1); application and reflection (session 2), (see Appendix 1).

PHASE	TEACHING OBJECTIVES	LEARNING OUTCOMES
OPENING	Speaking exercise (tapping into prior knowledge; recalling and sharing personal experiences).	SO1 - Observe how the 1·1·2 Emergency Phone Number works.
	Eliciting key vocabulary (<i>life-threatening situations, caller, dispatcher, injuries, first-aid, mediate</i>). SS watch a video about the 1·1·2 - European Emergency Number and answer 5 questions (multiple-choice exercise).	
INFORMING	SS read a piece of news in English reporting a motor vehicle collision crash in Torrevieja (Alicante).	SO1 - Understand the protocol for dealing with emergencies (e.g., car accidents) in public services.
	SS sight-translate (SP > ENG) the questions from the question plan (emergency protocol).	SO3 - Create a simulated emergency call (scripted) between a witness and an interpreter/dispatcher.
	SS imagine and complete the call interview between an English-speaking witness and the mediator/interpreter/dispatcher at 1·1·2 using the information provided on the news article (ENG > ENG). SS become actors simulating the call with the script they prepared together. Intratextual and extratextual factors are shared with SS to achieve a more realistic result.	GO2 - Become aware of the mediator and interpreter's task at the public emergency services.
APPLYING	Simultaneously, while recreating the scripted call, SS are encouraged to complete the emergency call report in Spanish that will be sent to the first response emergency services in the area. SS summarize the information from the call and use the Spanish emergency services jargon (ENG > SP).	GO2 - Become aware of the mediator/interpreter's task at the public emergency services. SO1 - Implement the protocol for dealing with emergencies in public services.

SS Listen to the simulated call provided by the teacher and compare their call reports (ENG > ENG).	GO3 - Develop listening and writing skills in accordance with the mediation process.
<i>Improvised simulation</i> . Using the information from another news report, SS reproduce a call between the English-speaking witness and the interpreter/mediator/dispatcher at the "1·1·2 Comunitat Valenciana" Emergency Services. Intratextual and extratextual factors are shared with SS to achieve a more realistic result.	SO2 - Apply linguistic and cultural knowledge in life-saving settings. SO3 - Create a simulated emergency call between a witness and an interpreter/dispatcher (scripted & improvised).
<i>Remote interpreting</i> . SS simulate a phone mediation between a police officer and the witness. SS discuss the challenges that interpreters/mediators/dispatchers deal with while managing emergency calls in foreign languages.	SO4 - Formulate an emergency call report for the emergency services containing all the relevant information for the resolution of the emergency.
REFLECTING SS match different varieties of translating, interpreting and mediating tasks with the exercises of the lesson. SS read about the 17 SDGs and connect the services provided at the 1·1·2 emergency number with the corresponding target of the UN Agenda 2030. SS take a quick look at the <i>Reference Framework of Competences for Democratic Culture and intercultural dialogue</i> and reflect about their learning experience choosing three competences that they have developed during the tasks. SS create a word cloud on <i>Mentimeter</i> with all the items from the framework. SS complete a survey on Google forms about the learning results.	SO5 - Identify and apply different varieties of the translational activity used in emergencies. GO1 - Identify and reflect on the ethical principles of sustainability (UN Agenda 2030) and the role of mediators and interpreters. GO4 - Promoting professional mediation skills.

Figure 6. Stages of the Deeper Learning Episode

5.1. Stage 1: Opening

Previous knowledge, both linguistic and cultural, was activated through questions related to the emergency numbers in the different countries of origin of the participants and their experiences (as users) with this public service. In this first open class discussion, part of the learners expressed their ignorance of the existence of interpreters and mediators in this service and, after a brief research through official web pages, great differences were detected regarding the linguistic services that each country makes available to citizens in life-threatening situations. At the end of the oral expression activity, a video² showing the European Public Emergency Service and how it works was shown. The

² European Parliament. (2010). *112 - European Emergency Number* [Video file]. YouTube. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=qAqOeFGshE>.

students carried out the oral comprehension task and shared their answers (see exercise 1, Appendix 1).

5.2. Stage 2: Informing

In order to understand the emergency protocols to protect the right to life, the class read a news story about a traffic accident with injuries and identified the key information for the resolution of the incident (see exercise 2, Appendix 1). Subsequently, the learners reflected on the emergency services with which, as MIPESs, they should interact with in order to report the event, concluding that it would be necessary to contact the police, for the cordoning off of the scene; firefighters for the extrication of the trapped person and ambulance service, for the evacuation of the victim. The learners also acknowledged that the jurisprudence, protocols and duties of medical services and security forces may differ from one country to another.

In a cooperative way, the trainees familiarised themselves with the questions in the protocols that should be asked to the witness at the scene over the telephone (see exercise 3, Appendix 1). To do this, first, text mediation (Nord and Piccardo 2020) comes into play: the key words corresponding to the protocolised questions for the type of emergency were provided in Spanish, since the information is available in this simplified form on the emergency room communications software. Secondly, the students reformulated the terms to turn them into questions for interaction with the citizens in their first language (English). Concepts, cultural differences and linguistic structures were also activated through this learning stage so that telephone communication in emergencies could be successfully handled in different contexts (figure 2, phase 0). The text mediation strategies that were activated at this time consisted of processing texts and adapting language (Nord and Piccardo 2020).

5.3. Stage 3: Applying

Once the interview questions were ready, the learners tried to complete the interview by imagining the citizens responses using the information in the news report (figure 2, phase 1) and, by doing this this, they obtained the information in order to carry out the first scripted simulation exercise. Students were able to prepare their roles using the Aronson's puzzle technique (Slavin 1995; García et al. 2012), where witnesses together thought about what they would say during the interview using the information from the news article while all MIPESs rehearsed their questions.

After some feedback provided by the instructor in their groups of experts, the first scripted simulation took place (see exercises 4, 5 and 6,

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Appendix 1), in preparation for the final exercise, an unscripted roleplay. In this way, we progressively implemented the varieties of simulation exercises in interpreter training stipulated by Fernández Pérez (2012, 2015).

Finally, the class listened to the traffic accident simulated call in English between the MIPESs and the witness based on the information in the news clipping (see exercise 7, Appendix 1)³, this provided an example of what the final simulation task should be like.

Both in this stage and in the following, the future Translation and Interpreting professionals had the opportunity to work in different rooms through the “breakout groups” option in *Blackboard Collaborate Ultra*. This allowed participants to interact with each other in a closer way (pairs and triads) while doing the practice or comparing their answers.

The possibility of interacting with the teacher in an individualized way to solve doubts and corrections allowed reducing the levels of anxiety and nervousness, essential in the second language class (Krashen 1982). As a result, the group discussions were more fruitful and enriching, as the students felt more confident in sharing their ideas and helping others after having worked as a team previously and having received advice and comments from the teacher in private.

At this point, once the basics of Telephonic Dialogue Interpreting and Mediation in Public Emergency Services had been established, the trainees were ready to develop their own simulations in a more improvised and natural way. They were provided with another newspaper cut-out with a similar structure to the previous one so that, after a short preparation time, they could recreate the conversation between the caller and the MIPESs in English while completing the institutional call reports in Spanish (see exercises 8 and 9, Appendix 1); (figure 2, phase 2).

Finally, the degree of difficulty was increased when they were proposed to perform a subsequent telephonic dialogue interpretation with a local police officer on site (figure 2, phase 3) requesting language services in order to interview the English-speaking citizen and complete the witness statement (see *follow up* exercise, Appendix 1)⁴.

³ Alarcón-García, Verónica. (2023). *112 Call Simulation & Report* [Video file]. YouTube. <https://youtu.be/jpy89qQeZhI>

⁴ Alarcón-García, Verónica. (2023). *Learning to Interpret and Mediate in the 112 Emergency Phone Line Through Roleplay – Final Exercise* [Video file]. YouTube. <https://youtu.be/7qEg3IK62q0>

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Follow up. After the *call report* is sent your help is essential (SP < > ENG).

When the police arrives at the scene, they need to talk to the witnessess to take a statement in order to fill up an “*acta declaratoria*” (witness statement). The officer calls back to the emergency phone number requesting the services of the interpreter to gather the following information:

1. ¿Ha observado usted la conducta del conductor?
2. ¿El conductor iba pendiente de la carretera? ¿Hacia gestos extraños o miraba su teléfono móvil?
3. ¿Se ha cruzado un animal suelto (perro)?
4. ¿Conducía a gran velocidad? ¿Ha dado un giro brusco o realizado un derrapaje? ¿Venía haciendo carreras con otro vehículo?
5. ¿Podría aportar otro tipo de información que fuera de interés para la investigación policial?

Could you sight translate the questions quickly? When you are ready, scan the code to practise the conversation.

Figure 7. Example of a preparatory activity for Telephonic Dialogue Interpreting in Public Emergency Services

The material used in this case was another recording with visual elements that left spaces in silence so that the students, in their role as interpreters, could complete the conversation between the police officer and the witness.

The learners were applying some mediation techniques and strategies such as relaying specific information in speech and in writing, translating a written text in speech and in writing, note taking, summarising, managing interaction and adapting language (Nord and Piccardo 2020).

Many interesting observations regarding this type of interactions arouse and the complexity to fill out the call report by the professional interpreter in Spanish, while conversing in English, in order to mediate with the administration, using the abbreviations and jargons of these Emergency Response Teams, did not go unnoticed. The class was made aware of the skills and abilities that the MIPESs need in their day-to-day task (figure 16).

5.4. Stage 4: Reflecting

After the adrenaline rush, the participants had a few moments to read the theoretical description of the Mediation and Interpretation techniques that had been used throughout the activity and, in small groups, connected them to each exercise (see exercise 10, Appendix 1). They were also able to reflect on the challenges and difficulties faced by MIPESs throughout the process and how their work responds to the

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demands of the Sustainable Development Goals (see exercise 11, Appendix 1).

To conclude the activity, they completed a questionnaire based on the task objectives and a work cloud with the main Competences for a Democratic Culture framework (COE 2016) (see *self-assessment*, Appendix 1).

6. Results

The results of the qualitative study demonstrate the willingness of the scholars to work on the *English Language B* courses in the Degree in Translation and Interpreting in an applied and transversal way. Through the final survey (see the complete document with the link in the footnote⁵), the students showed, unanimously, their interest in continuing to develop skills and learning languages by establishing connections with other subjects in the curriculum.

I can apply what I have learnt during the task on other courses of the Study Programme.
16 responses

I would like the Language B English courses in the Translation and Interpreting Degree to include active methodologies like role-play or project-based learning with practical activities.
16 responses

Figures 8 and 9. Self-assessment results (Q10 and 11)

This practical and collaborative method of meaningful acquisition of skills for the performance of sustainable translation work had a strong impact on the high level of motivation during the completion of the tasks, also reflected in a high rate of student participation.

Almost 70% of the class considered that they had learnt about different varieties of the translational activity used in the emergency setting (mediation, sight translation, dialogue interpreting).

⁵ https://gplaneta-my.sharepoint.com/:b:/g/personal/uvag2a_psoplaneta_com/EQ250j3kK-IOqUk_UnVsYs0B7Ur0c7RLCUh4LtPRdwW90A?e=BirKzJ

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I can identify and apply different varieties of the translational activity used in emergencies.
16 responses

Figure 10. Self-assessment results (Q5)

While 75% considered that they had the opportunity to apply linguistic and cultural knowledge in life-saving settings.

I have been able to apply linguistic and cultural knowledge in life-saving settings.
16 responses

Figure 11. Self-assessment results (Q6)

On the whole, the learners stated that the task had allowed them to learn more about the SDGs of the 2030 Agenda and the importance of the role of MIPESs within the principles of sustainability.

I can identify the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).
16 responses

Thanks to the task I am more concerned about the role of the mediators and interpreters within the principles of sustainability.
16 responses

Figures 12 and 13 (Q8 and 9)

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In the final space reserved for reflection, the class, through the following word cloud, shared the competences that, almost without realising, they had worked on towards the commitment to a democratic culture.

Figure 14. Word cloud generated cooperatively on *Mentimeter.com* in the reflecting stage within the Framework of Competences for a Democratic Culture

In this graphical representation, greater prominence is given to words that appeared more frequently in the students' responses during the final stage. Within this framework of competences, regarding "values": the learners highlighted valuing democracy, justice and human rights. Concerning "attitudes": self-efficacy, civic-mindedness, responsibility and respect were pointed out. With respect to "skills": we observe a higher importance of communicative skills, conflict-resolution skills and critical thinking. Finally, with reference to "knowledge and critical understanding": the learners underlined understanding of the self and understanding of language and communication and of the world.

7. Discussion and conclusions

Throughout the years, this linguistic course with very specific learning objectives and results was taught following the structure of General English textbooks based on a grammatical progression, which were clearly not focused on the specific needs of the learners of this official Degree.

The state of affairs seemed to have reached a turning point where further progress had to be made towards meaningful learning. Considering previous studies, this had to be done by following the scheme in figure 1 and examining the specific learner's profile and attitudes in

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order to shift towards a student-centered learning (SCL) approach (Collins & O'Brien 2003).

On the one hand, some of these attitudes were expressed in the surveys regarding satisfaction with the teaching activity, where students had shown willingness to connect language courses to the professional world and emphasised the need to apply the concepts in practical and relevant activities. It was made obvious that future translators and interpreters were dissatisfied with the traditional dynamics in foreign language courses.

Student A: "Solo se concentra en la competencia gramatical, sin trabajar las otras competencias lingüísticas, como la comprensión y expresión orales. No hay ningún trabajo sobre los aspectos culturales, tan necesarios para un traductor."

Student B: "Solo [se usan] los materiales teóricos del libro de texto, y no se han realizado muchas actividades prácticas en las clases, todo era prácticamente teoría."

Figure 15. Comments from past student satisfaction surveys

On the other hand, the different language proficiency levels of the trainees within the same class, were posing a challenge when planning and designing language courses, since learning opportunities for all learners had to be provided regardless of their language background.

In view of the above, on the assumption that simulation methodologies allow future translators and interpreters to develop their knowledge, skills and professional attitudes through experiential learning (Learning by Doing) (Roberts 2011), with this project we intended to transform a language module from a traditional language-led course to a competence-based one which could be more comprehensive and meaningful.

By implementing active methodologies set in real-life contexts through role-playing, the learners were able to apply and internalize, in a practical way, the more conceptual knowledge (also acquired in other subjects of the curriculum) and anticipate obstacles that will most likely be presented to the interpreter in the performance of their work, as well as to develop the appropriate strategies to overcome them (Fernández 2015, 262).

These strategies should not go unnoticed within the framework of Mediation and Telephonic Dialogue Interpreting in the context of access to information and the protection of fundamental freedoms. The great challenge for professionals in this field does not concern the linguistic issues (since it is possible to anticipate the thematic areas and prepare glossaries according to the typologies of incidents), but the complex

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interweaving of competences and skills that is activated (figure 16) and that can also be worked on in the *English Language B* class through didactic programmes based on cooperative experiences such as the one carried out in this study.

Figure 16. Skills and abilities activated while learning to Interpret and Mediate in the 1·1·2 Emergency Phone Line through Roleplay (using as a reference the model provided by the PACTE Group, 2003)

In conclusion, the pedagogical programming was proved to be appropriate to fulfil the objectives of the study, the didactic proposal and the course fundamentals. Foreign language teaching and learning processes in official Degree programmes are possible within a broader framework that encompasses all the skills of the Competence of Translation and Interpreting, basic to building bridges between the public administration and its citizens.

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